

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

INTEGRATION OF NATURAL SCIENCES IN THE TEACHING OF MATHEMATICS IN PRIMARY GRADES

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Abstract

The purpose of the study is to determine the effect of integrating natural sciences into mathematics lessons on primary-grade students' learning motivation and knowledge acquisition.

Relevance of the study: In the modern education system, the integration of various subjects in primary grades is of great importance for developing students' analytical thinking and real-life application skills.

Method: The study is based on theoretical analysis, practical teaching models, and teaching experience. It explores the integration of mathematics with astronomy, physics, and geography in primary grades.

Integration broadens students' thinking by combining different fields of knowledge. This approach helps students connect topics and apply their knowledge to real-life situations. According to various studies, integration in primary grades increases students' attention, makes topics more meaningful, and broadens their worldview.

Integrating mathematics with astronomy, physics, and geography helps students understand natural phenomena and analyze them mathematically. For example, topics such as measuring distances between planets in astronomy, calculating speed and time in physics, and map reading and analyzing statistical data in geography are combined with mathematics to provide students with more practical knowledge.

Integrating mathematics with natural sciences enriches primary school teaching and helps students develop essential skills for their future. This approach enhances their analytical thinking abilities and allows them to find logical connections and understand the world more deeply. Integrated educational methods not only increase teaching effectiveness but also motivate students to engage with real-life topics, solve problems, and find innovative solutions. The joint study of mathematics and natural sciences will create a strong foundation for students to solve complex problems they will encounter in the future and equip them with the skills required in the 21st century.

Conclusion: Integration with natural sciences ensures that students understand the relationship between mathematics and life, increases interest, and organizes the learning process more comprehensively and effectively.

Keywords: Integration, primary school, teaching mathematics, natural sciences, analytical thinking.

1. Introduction

In the modern education system, integration plays a key role in establishing interdisciplinary connections and promoting a deeper and more nuanced understanding of knowledge. This approach is of great importance, especially in primary grades, for developing students' skills in making connections between different subjects. Primary grades have great potential in terms of integrating mathematics with natural sciences, increasing students' interest, linking mathematical knowledge with real life, and encouraging them to learn the basics of natural sciences.

Natural sciences, especially astronomy, physics, and geography, provide extensive opportunities for the application and understanding of mathematical concepts. For example, when topics such as the concept of measurement and time, the study of figures, and the analysis of statistical data are combined with natural phenomena, they help students form both a mathematical and a general worldview.

The article will examine the importance of integration with natural sciences in teaching mathematics in primary grades, the methods of applying integration, and the impact on students' knowledge and skills.

The purpose of the study is to emphasize the importance of integration with natural sciences in teaching primary mathematics and to investigate the possibilities of applying this approach in the teaching process. The article aims to demonstrate how the integration of mathematics with natural phenomena affects the deep understanding of mathematical concepts in students, the development of analytical and critical thinking skills. In addition, how integration can boost students' interest and increase their motivation to learn is investigated.

Relevance of the study: In the modern education system, the integration of various subjects is of great importance for developing students' analytical thinking and real-life application skills. In particular, the integration of natural sciences, including astronomy and physics, with mathematical concepts in primary grades allows students to better understand the practical application of these concepts and their connection with everyday life. Integration makes the teaching process more interesting and meaningful, and at the same time forms 21st-century skills.

Method: In the study, the integration of mathematics with astronomy, physics, and geography in primary grades was carried out based on theoretical analyses, practical teaching models, and teaching experience.

The topic we are investigating is important in terms of modernizing teaching methods in education and improving the quality of education. Integrating the connections between natural sciences and mathematics into the curriculum will create conditions for the development of interdisciplinary thinking in students and the formation of interest in mathematics.

2. The role of integration in teaching

The importance of the integration approach in teaching methodology

Integration is a methodological approach that ensures the integration and coordination of different areas of knowledge and skills in education and the holistic assimilation of this knowledge by students. This approach makes it possible to coordinate different subjects in the teaching process and helps students to understand, apply, and use the knowledge they have acquired in more deeper way in life situations. Integration is not only a tool for organizing topics in teaching but also a means of providing students with thinking and analytical skills. At the same time, it develops students' skills not only in theoretical knowledge but also in applying this knowledge to real-life situations and using it in practice (Sriraman, 2008).

Various studies have clearly shown the importance of the integration approach in teaching methodology. As in the upper grades, integration in primary grades also helps to build students' knowledge in a stronger and more comprehensive way. Treacy (Treacy, 2018) notes that integration increases students' attention in the learning process and contributes to making the topics studied more meaningful. Integrations applied in primary grades not only provide students with both scientific and social skills but also expand their worldview.

The Role of Integration in Developing Thinking and Worldviews of Primary School Students

The role of integration in primary school education is not limited to increasing academic knowledge but also has a positive impact on the social and emotional development of students. Integration is an approach aimed at developing students' thinking skills. Natural sciences, especially astronomy and physics, when combined with mathematics in primary schools, develop students' analytical thinking and problem-solving skills. For example, combining the subject of astronomy with mathematics strengthens students' critical thinking and analytical thinking skills by teaching them topics such as measuring time, planetary motion, and calculating distances (Pirverdiyeva, 2022).

The integration of mathematics with natural sciences allows students to explain existing scientific concepts with concrete examples and to understand these concepts more deeply. Students understand that mathematics is not only a field related to addition, subtraction, and general calculation, but also how it is applied in the analysis of natural phenomena and real life. This approach broadens students' thinking and encourages them to think more creatively.

Integration develops students' worldviews. According to modern educational theories, the development of students' worldviews is possible by

using the connections between different subjects in a broader and more complex way. Purposeful integration of subjects allows students to understand nature and the world more deeply. For example, connecting astronomy and geography with mathematics helps students better understand the phenomena occurring on Earth and in space and analyze these phenomena mathematically.

3. Connecting Mathematics to Science

Connecting astronomy and mathematics is crucial in elementary school to explain various scientific concepts, including distance measurement, timekeeping, and mathematical models of planetary motion. For example, measuring distances between planets requires mathematical calculations, which teach students the fundamental principles of measurement, conversion, and calculation. Astronomy uses various methods to measure distances, including astronomical units (AU). This provides students with fundamental knowledge in both mathematics and astronomy.

Mathematical models of planetary motion are based on Kepler's laws. Kepler's laws demonstrate that the orbits of planets are elliptical and that the speed of movement in these orbits changes over time. This is an important topic that demonstrates the application of mathematics to astronomy (Newton, 1687/2007). Integrating such topics allows students to think more deeply in both mathematics and science.

The integration of physics and mathematics helps students understand the natural phenomena they encounter in their daily lives and build mathematical models to explain these phenomena. One of the most commonly used concepts in physics is units of measurement: length, time, speed, and mass. Connecting mathematics with these concepts provides students with the skills to convert units of measurement, simplify expressions, calculate physical quantities, and analyze data.

Speed and time calculations are basic concepts in physics. For example, speed is calculated by dividing distance by time ($v = \frac{S}{t}$). These calculations develop

students' mathematical skills in both physics and mathematics. The integration of speed and time issues in physics provides students with an understanding of the application of mathematics to natural sciences. This integration provides students with an understanding of how mathematics is related to practical life and a deeper understanding of natural phenomena (Islamzadeh, Allahverdiyev & Mammadov, 2024).

The integration of geography and mathematics provides students with the skills to analyze geographical data, use maps, and interpret statistical data. The geographic coordinate system teaches students to identify locations on maps and calculate distances between those locations. Using geographic coordinate systems in geography lessons helps students understand how mathematics relates to life. For example, the distance between two points can be found using the Pythagorean theorem or other mathematical calculations (National Research Council, 2001).

In addition, statistical data in geography is evaluated through mathematical analysis. Students use appropriate statistical methods in reading maps and analyzing geographic data. Statistical data analysis provides students with the skills to interpret data presented through tables, graphs, and diagrams and to make decisions (Mayer & Moreno, 2003). This is a useful approach to integrating both geography and mathematics.

4. Practical approaches to the application of integration

Selecting topics that are appropriate for the age and knowledge level of students

When applying integration, the age and knowledge levels of students should be taken into account. In primary grades, students typically have basic mathematical knowledge, so integrated lessons should begin with simple and practical problems. For instance, in grade 1, students can be introduced to simple astronomical problems related to equality and addition operations. Such problems not only develop students' mathematical thinking but also provide them with an introduction to astronomy. For older age groups, more complex problems can be introduced, such as planetary motion and time-distance relationships.

When integrating mathematics and natural sciences, it is important to present topics in a way that is appropriate for the students' age. This approach allows students to understand not only the application of mathematics but also natural phenomena (Kilpatrick, Swafford, & Findell, 2001).

Examples of integration in elementary school mathematics lessons

Problem 1: The International Space Station takes 736 minutes

to orbit the Earth 8 times. How many minutes does it take for this station to orbit the Earth once? (Isayev Z. et al., 2022).

Understanding: Given: The time it takes for the International Space Station to orbit the Earth. Condition: The International Space Station takes 736 minutes to orbit the Earth 8 times. Need to find: How many minutes does this station take to orbit the Earth once?

Planning: The problem is simple; it will be solved with one action.

Solution: How many minutes does the International Space Station take to orbit the Earth once?
 $736 \text{ min.} : 8 = 92 \text{ min.}$

Answer: The International Space Station took 92 minutes to orbit the Earth once.

The problem is solved correctly. It integrates mathematics and natural sciences and natural sciences,

enhancing theoretical and practical knowledge of students. By solving this problem, students develop the following skills:

- *Development of mathematical skills:* Using the given information, they calculate the time spent for one period by performing division operations.

- *Logical thinking:* They analyze the problem and identify the relationship between the data.

- *Applied mathematics:* They apply mathematical knowledge to solve a real-life problem.

- *Understanding of science and technology:* They gain information about the movement of the International Space Station and develop a general understanding of space exploration.

- *Refinement of the concept of time:* They enhance the ability to work with time measurements.

Problem 2. The planet that is closer to the Sun takes less time to complete a complete orbit around it. For example, Saturn completes one complete orbit around the Sun in 10759 days, Neptune in 60182 days, and Jupiter in 4355 days. Which of these planets should be written in place of the "?" signs? (Isayev Z. et al., 2023).

Understanding: Given: Planets that are closer to the Sun spend less time orbiting it.

Condition: Saturn completes one complete orbit around the Sun in 10759 days, Neptune in

60 182 days, and Jupiter in 4355 days. Guess: Which of these planets should be named instead of the "?" signs?

Planning: It is advisable to solve the problem with explanations.

Solution: The problem gives the time it takes each planet to complete one orbit around the Sun.

Saturn
10 759 days

Neptune
60 182 days

Jupiter
4 355 days

What we are required to do is to list the names of these planets in ascending order of their periods. That is, the planet with the shortest period should be first, and the planet with the longest period should be last. Thus, the order in ascending order of numbers would be as follows:

Jupiter
4 355 days

Saturn
10 759 days

Neptune
60 182 days

Jupiter – 4 355 days (shortest period, i.e. closest planet to the Sun)

Saturn – 10 759 days (medium-length period)

Neptune – 60 182 days (longest period, i.e. farthest planet from the Sun)

This can be schematically described as follows:

Answer: In place of the "?" signs, Jupiter, Saturn, and Neptune will be written in order, starting from the one closest to the Sun.

Check: $4355 < 10759 < 60182$

By solving this problem, students acquire the following skills:

- Comparing the orbital periods of planets around the Sun;
- Understanding astronomical measurements and differences in the orbits of planets;
- Developing mathematical calculation skills;
- The ability to draw correct conclusions by comparing data.

Problem 3: When the Moon revolves around the Earth, the closest distance between them is 363 300 km, and the farthest distance is 405 500 km. Approximately how many thousands of kilometers are the closest and farthest distances from the Moon to the Earth? To what degree do you round these distances to get the same numbers? (Isayev Z. et al., 2023).

Understanding: Given: The closest and farthest distances between the Moon and the Earth as they orbit the Earth. Condition: The closest distance between the Moon and the Earth as they orbit the Earth is 363300 km, and the farthest distance is 405500 km. Find: 1. Approximately how many thousands of kilometers are the closest and farthest distances from the Moon to the Earth? 2. To what degree do these distances round to get the same numbers?

Planning: Let's solve the problem with questions.

1) Approximately how many thousands of kilometers are the closest and farthest distances from the Moon to the Earth?

$$363300 \text{ km} < 405500 \text{ km}$$

The closest distance between the Moon and the Earth is 363300 km, and the farthest distance is 405500 km.

2) To what power do these distances give the same numbers?

The same result is obtained when the distances are rounded to the nearest hundredth.

$$363300 \text{ km} \approx 400000 \text{ km}$$

$$405500 \text{ km} \approx 400000 \text{ km}$$

Answer: If the distances are rounded to the nearest hundredth, the same number – 400 000 km - is obtained.

By solving this problem, students acquire the following skills:

- They understand how mathematics is related to astronomy and other natural sciences.
- They learn to apply mathematical calculations to natural phenomena by making connections between different subjects.
- They are able to use rounding operations in real life and simplify the results.
- They use mathematical knowledge to understand and analyze astronomical data.

Problem 4: The International Space Station travels approximately 27615 km in 1 hour as it orbits the Earth. It completes one orbit around the Earth in 1 hour and 30 minutes. How many hours does it take for the space station to complete 2 orbits? Approximately how many kilometers does it travel in this time? (Isayev Z. et al., 2023).

Understanding: Given: The distance traveled by the International Space Station while orbiting the Earth

Condition: The International Space Station travels approximately 27615 km in 1 hour while orbiting the Earth. It completes one orbit around the Earth in 1 hour and 30 minutes.

Need to find: How many hours will it take the Space Station to complete 2 orbits? How many kilometers will it cover in this time?

Planning: Let's solve the problem in a planned manner.

Solution: 1) How many hours will it take the Space Station to complete 2 orbits?

$$1 \text{ hours } 30 \text{ min.} \cdot 2 = 2 \text{ hours } 60 \text{ min.} = 3 \text{ hours}$$

2) Approximately how many kilometers will the space station travel during this time?

$$27615 \text{ km} \cdot 3 = 82845 \text{ km}$$

Answer: The space station travels approximately 82845 km during this time.

By solving this problem, elementary school students develop the following skills:

- Calculation skills: Students learn to perform operations with given information and derive results.
- Understanding time and distance: Students grasp the relationship between the time elapsed during an action and the distance covered.
- Working with large numbers: Students perform calculations using large numbers.
- Logical thinking skills: Students learn to think logically based on the given information.
- Applying operations sequentially: Students learn to reach the correct result by applying a series of simple operations in sequence.
- Integration of astronomy and mathematics: Students learn the interplay of these two fields by applying mathematical operations to solve problems related to astronomy.

5. The impact of integration on the development of students' thinking

The Impact of Integrating Mathematics and Science on Student Motivation

Integrating mathematics and science is an effective approach for enhancing student motivation. Integration makes lessons more engaging and enjoyable, which boosts students' interest in the subjects. Integration demonstrates to students how mathematics and science are applied in real life, highlighting the practical importance of this knowledge in everyday situations. When students realize that mathematics helps them understand natural phenomena, their interest in the lesson increases, and their motivation to learn increases. (PISA, 2012).

In general, creating interdisciplinary connections helps students to be more open-minded about different topics and more enthusiastic in their approach to lessons. Integration of mathematics and science enriches students' learning experiences and connects lessons with real-life problems, ultimately enhancing the quality of teaching.

Developing students' analytical and critical thinking skills

The application of integration positively impacts on the development of students' analytical and critical thinking skills. In mathematics and science classes, students' analytical thinking, data analysis, and problem-solving skills are reinforced. Integration allows students to apply mathematical models and approaches to thinking about natural phenomena. This enables them to develop stronger analytical thinking and make sound decisions by analyzing data in depth (Artigue, 2009).

Critical thinking equips students with the ability to evaluate information and analyze theories and approaches. The integration of mathematics and science teaches students to critically analyze both mathematical formulas and science-related information. This approach provides a deeper and more comprehensive understanding of the topics.

The impact of interdisciplinary connections on learning outcomes

Interdisciplinary connections significantly enhance learning outcomes. The integration of mathematics and science provides students with a more holistic and comprehensive learning experience by

combining the knowledge they have acquired from different subjects. This approach helps students understand topics more holistically, rather than isolating them. When the knowledge learned is interconnected, students understand topics more deeply, leading to improved learning outcomes (Beane, 1997).

Interdisciplinary connections ensure that students are more actively involved in the learning process, as understanding the connections between topics increases their interest. This approach encourages students not only to learn information, but also to apply it in practice. As a result, this method helps students achieve greater success throughout their education (PISA, 2015).

6. Conclusions and recommendations

Advantages and Challenges of Integration in the Educational Process

Integrating mathematics and science in the educational process offers numerous advantages. Integration helps students apply their knowledge to real-life situations, fostering greater interest and enthusiasm for the learning process. This approach allows students to better understand the relationship between mathematics and science in everyday life, thereby developing their thinking and analytical skills. Establishing connections between mathematics and science increases students' interest in these subjects and enhances their motivation for learning. (Boaler, 2002; PISA, 2015).

However, there are also several challenges in implementing integration. One of the primary challenges involves the preparation of lesson plans and teaching materials. Teachers must possess knowledge and skills in multiple subjects and prepare materials that integrate this knowledge. This requires additional time, effort, and resources. Moreover, teachers may find it challenging to teach both areas in a balanced and purposeful manner while effectively applying interdisciplinary connections. Maintaining this balance is crucial for both subject teaching and the effectiveness of integration (Beane, 1997).

Suggestions for expanding integration methods in educational programs

Several suggestions can be employed to expand integration in educational programs. First, it is important to organize training and development programs for teachers. Teachers should deepen their understanding of how integration is applied in teaching and become more informed about the benefits of this approach (Artigue, 2009). The development of appropriate teaching materials is also a critical issue. To establish stronger connections between natural sciences and mathematics, appropriate interdisciplinary approaches should be considered in the development of lesson plans and resources. This will enable teachers to apply integration more effectively in their lessons.

In addition, it would be appropriate to redesign educational programs in a structure that supports interdisciplinary connections and facilitates integration. Mathematics and science should not be taught in isolation but as interconnected and complementary disciplines (Beane, 1997). This

approach will enable students to understand the knowledge they are learning in a broader and more integrated context. To achieve this, changes should be made in the education system that facilitate the application of more integrated and comprehensive learning approaches. Thus, students will not only learn separate subjects, but will also learn to understand the connections between knowledge and apply them in real-life situations.

Prospects for future research

Future research on the role of integration in teaching should focus on several areas. First, it is important to study how the implementation of integration affects students' long-term educational outcomes. Existing research is mostly based on short-term outcomes, but studies that assess long-term development are important. In addition, studies that compare the effects of integration on students of different age groups should be conducted. Exploring how the connections between mathematics and science affect different age groups will help to better implement teaching methods (PISA, 2012).

In addition, research on the development of appropriate guidelines and resources for teachers to implement integration more effectively is important. It is also useful to examine best practices for incorporating teaching methods and interdisciplinary connections into lesson plans. Gathering more information about the challenges teachers face when implementing integration and how these challenges can be overcome could be an important direction for researchers (Boaler, 2002; Popkewitz & Fendler, 1999).

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